

Alstovenine, a New Indole Alkaloid Isolated from *Alstonia Venenatus* R. Br.

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Under the research programme on the chemical investigation of medicinal plants of the Apocynaceae family, it was intended to study the active principles of the stem bark of *Alstonia venenatus* R. Br. This species is distributed in the Deccan peninsula and enjoys reputation for its medicinal properties¹.

The chloroform extract of the dried and pulverised bark of *A. venenatus* was processed in the usual manner for separation of the bases. The basic material yielded on chromatography over Brockmann alumina two indole alkaloids, one of which crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 172° (yield 0.03%) and the other from ethylacetate in nodules, m.p. 192° (decomp.) (yield 0.006%). Homogeneity of the compounds has been established from paper chromatography (ascending) with butanol²: formic acid: water = 12:1:7 (R_f values, 0.61 and 0.80 respectively).

From the studies made so far, the alkaloid, m.p. 172°, appears to be a new one. It has been named as Alstovenine ($C_{22}H_{28}O_4N_2$). (Found: C, 68.54; H, 7.32; N, 7.22; Mass number, 384. $C_{22}H_{28}O_4N_2$ requires C, 68.75; H, 7.29; N, 7.29%). It is free from -NMe and -CMe and contains at least two active hydrogen atoms and two -OMe groupings, one of which is associated with a methoxycarbonyl. The fourth oxygen atom occurs as a hydroxyl. The tertiary nature of the alkaloid is established by the ready formation of a methiodide which crystallises from methanol in fine needles, m.p. 245° (decomp.).

The alkaloid absorbs light in the UV region: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 226 (log ϵ , 4.76), 272 (log ϵ , 4.06), and 293 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 3.92); $\lambda_{shoulder}^{EtOH}$ 208 (log ϵ , 4.53), 286 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.00); λ_{min}^{EtOH} 245 (log ϵ , 3.72) and 290 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 3.91). The maximal and minimal positions undergo 2-4 $m\mu$ hypsochromic shifts in EtOH/0.1N-HCl. The IR spectrum of the alkaloid in nujol exhibits bands at 2.84 and 3.04 μ (-OH and >NH) and at 5.78 μ (ester carbonyl).

The base exhibits characteristic colour reactions (conc. nitric acid → green, Fröhde → light green changing to mossy green, Hopkins-Cole → greenish blue → dirty violet).

The spectral analysis of the base and its colour reactions suggest the presence of a 2,3-disubstituted indole nucleus in the compound. It responds to Haycock-Mader colour

1. Chopra, Nayer, and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 14.

reaction², specific for 7-methoxytetrahydro- β -carbolines³, which obviously confirms the presence of the 7-methoxy- β -carboline moiety in alstovenine. This observation is consistent with the UV data of the alkaloid.

Further structural investigation on alstovenine is in progress.

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2. *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc. (Sci. Ed.)*, 1957, **46**, 774.

3. Trojanek *et al.*, *Chem. Ind.*, 1961, 790.